

Bot Detection in Twitter

A deep multi-GCN approach

Abstract—Social media have now a multifaceted perspective and increased participation in people’s daily lives. Although they were initially built in the sphere of communication, their latest purposes concern the fields of information, grouping and advertising. Their enriched penetration of personal data have formed an axis that lurks dangers and threats. Twitter is one of the largest social platforms and disposes a strong impact in the formation and spread of ideas and opinions, which are mainly connected with socio-political issues. This global landscape has caused the appearance of different types of fake news, whose most dangerous and threatening origin is the ever-growing subset of Twitter users : ”Bots”. Therefore, the detection of those non-genuine accounts is something more than critical as our aim of limiting and eliminating them is urgent.

Index Terms—Social media, communication, information, fake news, Bots, detection

I. INTRODUCTION

TWITTER is one of the world’s largest social media platforms, with more than 500 millions users. It was launched in America, in 2006, by Jack Dorsey, Noah Glass, Biz Stone and Evan Williams. It is headquartered in San Francisco, California, having nowadays more than 25 branches around the world. Since 2012, more than 100 million users have generated 340 million tweets every day, while in 2019 the platform reached 330 million monthly active users, thus becoming - until February 2024 - the sixth most visited website in the world. From October of 2022, Twitter belongs to the famous billionaire Elon Musk.

The interesting but also dangerous statistic is that based on estimates made in 2020, 15 per cent of total accounts do not present genuine people, but malicious bots. This statistic was directly linked to the accusations against the platform for spreading misinformation and hate speech. These two behaviors have of course a great influence in the whole community of Twitter, which is deeply affected and suffered by false and devious opinions. The inevitable birth and spread of fake news has led to the urgent and crucial need for valid and reliable detection of the blameable bots. In short, this need is nothing else but a classification task, in which we will be able to separate the real and the fake users of Twitter. Numerous systems have provided various solutions in this concept, each one making good use of different mathematical models or data coming from Twitter.

II. RELATED WORK

There are several remarkable attempts in the classification task of bot detection in Twitter. In this section we will mention some previous relative systems and describe their

logic as well. Our goal is to investigate the different famous approaches and present their limitations.

A. Detecting with Algorithms and Classifiers

The following systems are some of the first approaches in bot detection problem of Twitter and contributed as famous baselines in the upcoming architectures.

Botometer focused more on the quantity and the variety of the extracted user attributes. Specifically, it concluded in more than 1000 features, created by personal info, content or metadata coming from Twitter API and processed by Random Forest. Although this specific algorithm presents some high scores without any extreme computational complexity, the final structure of the decision trees is significantly sensitive to new data.

Yang’s approach mainly focused on improving the scalability and generalization of the retrieved information. Specifically, instead of gathering personal profile data of the users, this proposed framework overcomes the API limits by collecting only user metadata. In this way, the model systematically analyzes more newly produced and diverse datasets and its interpretability is highly enhanced.

A completely divergent and special solution is called **Cresci**. In this approach, the online actions of the users are encoded and ensemble the DNA behavior. In other words, the actions of a user are displayed as encoded series of letters (P-L-P-C-F-F-..) where every letter has a different remarkable meaning, exactly like in the DNA’s chains. The unique formed string will then be provided in deeper calculating processes that will define the similarities among the users and their corresponding labels as a result, using the Longest Common Substring (LCS) as a metric.

Miller’s solution is exclusively based on famous clustering algorithms, which usually are used in unsupervised learning. In short, spam detection does not acquire a classification attitude in this case. DenStream and StreamKM++ are the two effective algorithms that take action in this system. The general purpose of the system is to investigate and detect the anomaly patterns lurking in some types of user metadata. DenStream is used in a iterative loop, calculating and defining the p-micro-clusters that contain all the genuine users and exclude the abnormal ones. On the other hand, StreamKM++ executes the kNN algorithm with a probabilistic initialization.

A dynamic deep dive into the Twittersphere was made by **Lee's** system, deploying some social honeypot profiles : fake accounts designed to attract and interact with content polluters (bots) and automatically gather data about their behavior. The authors included a classification framework that takes advantage of users features such as demographics, graph properties and tweet content in order to proceed to the final estimations about the users' identity, using Machine Learning Classifiers.

B. Detecting with Neural Networks

Recurrent Neural Networks played a vital role in tweets' preprocessing and in improving the accuracy of detectors as a result.

Wei's system gives solution in bot detection by making good use of a bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory model with three hidden layers. The initial tweets are firstly encoded and then create word embeddings, which are the original input of the model. After a fully connected three-layer hidden path, a Softmax activation function defines the final probabilistic result of the classification. The fact that there is no need for feature engineering - the proposed model uses only contextual content of the users - is displayed as a vital advantage of this system, making it an interesting baseline.

Kudugunta's approach consists of two core components : Tweet-Level Classification and Account-Level Classification. The first component contribute in detecting bots based on their tweets' content and metadata, by aggregating the output of an LSTM model ('GloVE') with the tweets metadata and produce the final results with a 2-layer Neural Network. On the other hand, in the second component, a minimal number of highly interpretable features is inputted to five different models, such as Logistic Regression, Random Forest Classifier and some others. The validation includes the undersampling procedures of SMOTENN and SMOTOMEK.

C. Detecting with Graph Convolutional Networks

Graph Convolutional Network is a game changer in the concept of detecting a fake account in a user community. In Twitter's scenario, the constructed graph is nothing else but an illustration of the different types of connections between the users.

The simple approach of **Alhosseini** is making good use of the basic user features that are retrieved from the Twitter API, when applying a Graph Convolutional Network in the neighbourhoods of users. Although its simplicity and minimality, this system displayed high scores in the early bots and was a significant baseline in the next developed systems.

BGSRD mainly focuses on the utilization of tweets in its efforts of detecting the bots, dividing the system into two crucial interactive sections : Text representations via BERT model and Graph Convolutional Network in text data. The

first is responsible for generating Next Sentence Predictions (NSP) and the learning of the model is maintained in the representations of the sentences' pairs and in the sentence level negative sampling as well. The second one takes into consideration the resulted representations of the previous section and uses them as input to an innovative Graph Convolutional Network, where posted documents and contained words play the role of nodes, which are weighty linked via TF-IDF and PPMI metric.

D. Detecting with Graph Attention Networks

The need of taking into consideration more than one type of connection in users' graph, led the systems to include attention mechanisms in Graph Convolutional Networks, in order to judge and count the weighted importance of each link.

BotMGAT's architecture takes advantage of numerical and boolean user attributes and includes multiple different views of Graph Neural Networks, each one developed in a unique kind of connection between the users (following links, interaction links, etc). An attention mechanism is also provided as a final layer, defining the weight and the importance of each component. With its transfer learning approach, the new fresh external user features and the MGAT Network will jointly produce the temporary labels, which will be respectively routed as input to a Machine Learning Classifier, like Random Forest.

HIN dedicates most of its architecture in the heterogeneity of the links among the users. Individual and distinctive graphs are constructed based on the same user dataset, but using different types of relations, like "following", "blocking", "liking", "mentioning", "quoting", "retweeting". Every graph is separately processed and pushed to Graph Attention Transformers, whose purpose is to give weights in the edges among the users and calculate the user's particular representations. The final process unit - called "Semantic Attention Networks" - is used to firstly obtain the importance of its relation and then fuse the final node representations under different relations.

E. Detecting with deep multimodal Networks

The retrieval of different kind of information from Twitter's API, and the continuous desire of increasing the metrics of a bot detection system, has driven the community to include multiple processing modules in their architectures.

SATAR presents three individual sub-networks : Profile-Property, Tweet-Semantic and Following-Follower Sub-Network. In the first scenario, 15 categorical, 5 numerical and 1 special encoded feature are concatenated and routed to a Fully Connected Layer. In the second scenario, Tweet-Level and Word-Level Encoders, both consisting of one bidirectional Recurrent Neural Network and accompanied by attention mechanisms, calculate the final representations of the user's

tweets semantics. Finally, the Following-Follower Sub-Network plays a centralist role by uniting the two separated previous Networks and introducing the user's neighbourhood. In this iterative procedure, the Co-Influence Aggregator is also interfered, which is responsible for providing the relative effects of each component.

BIC divides the general attributes of the user into two great categories :

- A. numerical and categorical
- B. personal description and tweets

The first one is fed to a Graph Attention Network, which is built based on the "following" relations between the users, while the second one is pushed to an NLP model ("RoBERTa"). The two provided results from Graph and Text Propagation are combined in a third Interactive Module, which is trained to learn the relative importance of these two sub-systems. An extra section is responsible for the detection of Semantic Consistency of the user's tweets, generating a final vector that "informs" about abnormal patterns in the posts of the users.

BotRGCN divides the general attributes of the user into four categories : description, tweets, numerical, categorical. The first two are fed to an NLP model ("RoBERTa"), while the other two are used as input in two separate Multi Layer Perceptrons. The four generated vectors are then concatenated and placed as the summaries of users in a Graph Neural Network. The related graph is heterogenous and created based on "following" and "followers" relations among the Twitter users.

F. Limitations

As we already mentioned, every implemented solution adds an extra useful value in the general problem, providing unique architectures that take advantage of different attributes, algorithms and models. Although they commonly accomplish high scores in their evaluations, they also present some drawbacks and limitations as well.

One of their biggest cons is that they do not really include the numerical metrics of the tweets. Apart from their language contribution, tweets have a lot to offer as for their numerical info, like :

likes, mentions, quotes, comments, retweets etc

One additional crucial limitation of all those described systems is that they have been trained in older datasets, like "TwiBOT-20" or even more previous versions. Bots are not simple pathetic entities that remain static over time. On the contrary, they always get evolved and become smarter in order to deal with the detection systems and filters. New more divergent bot accounts have been widely spreaded over the recent years, so continuous updating and adjustment are something more than critical nowadays.

Dataset	C-15	G-17	C-17	M-18	C-S-18	C-R-19	B-F-19	Twibot-20	Twibot-22
# Human	1,950	1,394	3,474	8,092	6,174	340	380	5,237	860,057
# Bot	3,351	1,090	10,894	42,446	7,102	353	138	6,589	139,943
# User	5,301	2,484	14,368	50,538	13,276	693	518	229,580	1,000,000
# Tweet	2,827,757	0	6,637,615	0	0	0	0	33,488,192	88,217,457
# Human Tweet	2,631,730	0	2,839,361	0	0	0	0	33,488,192	81,250,102
# Bot Tweet	196,027	0	3,798,254	0	0	0	0	33,488,192	6,967,355
# Edge	7,086,134	0	6,637,615	0	0	0	0	33,716,171	170,185,937

III. DATASET

"Twibot-22" is the most recent dataset of Twitter and is the one that will be utilized in our system. The previous versions had a difficulty in containing different types of genuine and fake accounts. In order to overtake this basic disadvantage, "Twibot-22" followed two important strategies while gathering users data :

1. Selecting users focusing on the distribution in their metadata.

2. Preferring users with greater diversity in their values.

So the total set of the Twitter users was built by a certain way. The algorithm begun from some seeds and then explored the community of users using Breadth First Search and the "following" relations. Given an already included user, the neighbourhoods - that will be also placed in the dataset - will be defined by one of the two rules above.

Except this special algorithm, which leads to more advanced and divergent users, "Twibot-22" is also known for its enhanced entities, like hastags, lists and tweets, and for its extra 12 corresponding connections among them as well.

Last but not least, the procedure of Data Annotation is more than crucial too. The classification was divided into three particular steps :

A. Labelization of 1000 initial users from experts.

B. Noisy generation of the labels for the total 1 million users. Based on the 1000 initial opinions and applying 8 manual mathematical functions and 7 different neural network models, the uncertain classification of the Twitter users is made.

C. Majority voting. The estimation of plausibility (by Snorkel) and a final Multi Layer Perceptron are combined in order to provide the final labels of the dataset.

All in all, "Twibot-22" ends up being the most trustworthy, accurate and consistent Twitter dataset, always compared to its competitors, providing more divergent and polymorphic entities and links.

IV. DESCRIPTION OF THE SYSTEM

Our system proposes the partition of the classification task into four different individual data paths :

1. Description of the user
2. Numerical and Categorical features of the user
3. Content of the tweets of the user
4. Numerical stats of the tweets of the user

Our dataset "Twibot-22" - through Twitter API - exposes a variety of different attributes for both users and tweets, which are appropriately selected and pushed to the four general categories above. Specifically, here are all the included fields :

TABLE I
NUMERICAL AND CATEGORICAL FEATURES OF THE USER

User
YearsOfExistence
NameLocation
FollowersCount
FollowingCount
TweetsCount
ListsCount
ProtectedOrNot
VerifiedOrNot
EntitiesCount

Some of the upper features have an obvious meaning. As for the rest ones, **YearsOfExistence** signify when the account was created, while **NameLocation** is an indicator for which personal info (name, username, location) are inserted into the profile. **EntitiesCount** informs about the number of the widgets (images, links, etc) that are contained in the profile dashboard.

All of the upper useful stats are easily understood and explained. The first and third category of data have a linguistic aspect and refer to the displayed description of the user and the text content of the tweets.

TABLE II
NUMERICAL STATS OF THE TWEETS OF THE USER

Tweet
Retweets
Replies
Quotes
Likes

Fig. 1. Feature retrieval of the four different datapaths

A. Architecture

The four separated categories of data are appropriately preprocessed and routed to four different Graph Convolutional Networks, which compute and provide the final four representative deep vectors. Finally, the deep vectors are aggregated and used as input to a final ultimate Multi Layer Perceptron, which leads to the binary result of the classification task.

B. Graph

The directed graph is constructed by taking into consideration these two principals :

1. The nodes represent the users of the Twitter
2. The edges refer to the "following" relations among the users

Fig. 2. Description and Tweets preprocessing

The Graph Convolutional Network also regard the attributes of the user as input.

In our case, the graph consists of 6000 different users, while each class own the half of them. The outbound degree of the user, as for the "following" links, was fairly placed as a critical priority in users' participation. In other words, a significant low density in the nodes' connections was really a state to avoid.

C. Linguistic data

As it is already highlighted before, the first and third category of data paths consist of text content. By taking advantage of the pretrained model :

"cardiffnlp/twitter-roberta-base"

both the description of the user and the tweets acquire a unique embedding of 768 numerical dimensions.

The embedding of the description of the user is directly defined as the corresponding vector of the user in the particular section. On the other hand, the embeddings of the tweets of a user are initially gathered and used to detect the most representative tweets, which are sorted and joined together to form the completed characteristic tweet of the user. This tweet is finally again encoded (by the model above) and its embedding is considered as the corresponding vector of the user in the third data path.

The following figure describes the way that description and tweets are processed and utilized to conclude to the final embeddings, which will be used as input to the Graph Neural Networks.

The representativeness of the tweets is defined by calculating the total differences among the tweets, based on

their embeddings. In this scenario, the tweet with the least sum of euclidean distances :

$$distances(tweet_j) = \sum_{i=0}^n \sqrt{emb(tweet_j)^2 + emb(tweet_i)^2} \quad (1)$$

is the one that represents the user in the most accurate way. The numerical features are normalized and scaled without experiencing any further preprocessing unit.

Fig. 3. Architecture of the system

V. EXPERIMENTS

Firstly we divide the total balanced set of 6000 users into three subsets :

train set : 70 per cent

validation set : 10 per cent

test set : 20 per cent

In order to correct the partial imbalances in the train set, the **SMOTE** oversampling procedure was utilized for both features and edges. Specifically, in the second case, the initial adjacency matrix of the "weak" class was expanded in three ways :

- A. Adding edges from new nodes to old ones
- B. Adding edges from old nodes to new ones
- C. Adding edges from new nodes to new ones

Fig. 4. Oversampling procedure in edges

In the classic case of features, the new users were generated by oversampling the vectors with the users' attributes.

The Graph Neural Networks were created using the **PyTorch Geometric** library and have all been trained with an Adam optimizer and a learning rate of $1e-5$. The final metrics were produced by repeatedly running our system 5 times and then averaging the individual results. The model was trained in 100 - 200 epochs minimizing the **CrossEntropyLoss** function of the same library. The same parameters were inserted in the final Multi Layer Perceptron.

As for the special internal parameters of every mathematical model, the four Graph Convolutional Networks and the Multi Layer Perceptron were defined by the following different applied pipelines :

TABLE III
MODELS' INTERNAL PIPELINES

GCN desc	GCN num	MLP
ConvLayer0 (x to 32)	ConvLayer0 (x to 16)	LinearLayer0 (x to 128)
ReLU	ReLU	ReLU
ConvLayer1 (32 to 8)	ConvLayer1 (16 to 8)	LinearLayer1 (128 to 64)
ReLU	ReLU	ReLU
		LinearLayer2 (64 to 8)
		ReLU
		LinearLayer3 (8 to 2)

The first GCN is applied in user descriptions and tweets, while the second one is used in numerical user attributes and tweets stats. The layers were carefully extracted considering smoothness based on the different inputs.

Accuracy, Precision, Recall and F1-Score were used as metrics in evaluating the introduced architecture. In the calculations, detecting the bot class is regarded as positive one.

VI. RESULTS

The table below displays the metrics for the individual partial components of our system, but also compares the final metrics with the ones produced by other famous architectures, which, in contrast, were trained and tested in :

Twibot-20

TABLE IV
METRICS OF OUR SYSTEM COMPARED WITH OTHER FAMOUS
ARCHITECTURES

	Description	Numerical	Tweets	Tweets stats	mGCN Detector	Alhosseini	Botometer	Cresci	BIC	BotRGCN	HIN
Accuracy	0.815	0.846	0.831	0.813	0.851	0.681	0.558	0.479	0.873	0.846	0.866
Precision	0.84	0.828	0.831	0.757	0.865				0.847		
Recall	0.786	0.876	0.853	0.925	0.835				0.934		
F1Score	0.809	0.851	0.835	0.832	0.849	0.731	0.489	0.107	0.888	0.870	0.882

Fig. 5. Losses across the training procedures of the four components

Compared to other state of the art architectures, our system leads high performances in a more competitive and divergent dataset :

TwiBot-22

It also exposes a higher level of **Precision**, making the positive predictions in bot detection more accurate.

The four initial individual components of our system present significantly sufficient and competitive metrics on their own. Specifically, Numerical Graph Neural Network lead high scores in Accuracy, while Tweets Stats have an extremely nice performance in Recall as well. However, the combination of all four components not only provides an average increase in all metrics, as it was expected, but also attaches a deeper approach in user's data. In short, the use of different kinds of user features ensures the bigger adaptability of the system in new divergent and unseen data. In other words, there is a higher balance and deeper collaboration among the semantics of a user's profile, so the detection of bots are more consistent and averagely more accurate.

Finally, a last but not least interesting point to be mentioned is the possibility of individual optimization, as for the four components. As the total system consists of four separated sections, the data retrieval, the feature preprocessing and the Graph Neural Network of every different scenario is able to be fully improved and optimized independently. This gives lots of hopeful promises to our future attempts of updating and upgrading our system.

VII. NEXT MOVES

There are a lot of possible moves that can be considered in the future in order to upgrade our system and improve its efficiency.

A. Updating our database

Keeping our database up to date plays a vital role in the whole concept of detecting the bots in Twitter. As we already mentioned, bots are always getting transformed into new divergent and more complicated creatures.

Bots progressively adapt to the detecting filters and adjust their behavior in order to increase their transparency. As a result, it is more than crucial for us to often include new and unseen data to our database. **TwiBot-22** is the most recent

version of retrieved data from Twitter API, but new updates are for sure about to come.

B. Enhancing the user features

Till now, the architecture of our system was exclusively based on the four features below :

1. Description of the user
2. Numerical attributes of the account
3. Personal tweets of the user
4. Numerical stats of the tweets

The defined pipeline of our system pushes these four features to four separated components, which include of course an individual Graph Neural Network.

An important section, that is missing from our architecture and can significantly boost the efficiency of our system, is the profile picture of the user. We can easily include the user's image in our data retrieval, and after some preprocessing actions, like pooling and flattening, we can appropriately route the extracted numerical embedding to a brand new fifth component with a corresponding Graph Convolutional Network. In this way, we are taking advantage of the independency among the subsystems and just append a new computational path with new useful semantic information, which provides an additional deep user vector that also participates in the final Multi Layer Perceptron. It is easily understood that after enhancing the user features and containing different kind of attributes, the multimodality of our system is getting larger and wider and the possibilities of improving its performance is heightened.

C. Experiencing new concatenating methods

The existing method of combining the extracted user vectors - and creating the input of the decisive Multi Layer Perceptron is simplistic and minimal one. In detail, the four deep vectors (of size 8) are joined together and shape a final representative vector (of size 32). In order to optimize the multimodality, we can attach an attention layer between the outputs of the four GCNs and the final MLP. In order to accomplish this, the implementation of the total system is required to become more dynamic. In other words, the training needs to take place across the whole pipeline and not partially or individually. Specifically, the results of each GCN will immediately inline be concatenated, according to the corresponding weights of each components. In this way, the contribution of each component (description, numerical, etc) in the final calculations may vary and the weights will be learnable parameters of the whole training path. To sum up, our model will be trained and - through backpropagation - will expose different levels of significance among the separated kinds of user features. This new implementation acquires higher importance in case our components proliferate in the future.

transparency and reliability of social media, but also for its challenging and competitive philosophy, as we are talking about a bidirectional concept.

Our mathematical models are trying to investigate the cores of the Twitter bots' nature, in order to restrict and limit their actions (spreading of fake news and ideas). Simultaneously, on the other hand, bots - on their side - are continuously adapting to the detection filters and attempting to diverge their behavior in order to escape.

As a result, the problem has inevitably a dynamic aspect, which increases the complexity and the need for consistent updating and upgrading.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Bot detection in Twitter is a classification task with special interest, not only because of its vital meaning in the